

Information System Types at Various Management Levels in Contemporary Organizations: An Overview

Mohammed Saleh Al-Tuhaifi

ECOFIGES Entrepreneurial Department, ESCT, University of Manouba, Tunisia.

Mohammed.tuhifi@gmail.com

Abstract

Information systems are prioritized in contemporary organizations. Considering them is a critical necessity for their continuity, expansion, and competitive empowerment. They focus on management information systems, which involve storing, processing, and analyzing data to transform them into valuable information used in planning or predicting the future under surrounding environmental conditions within organizations. Information systems are divided into several types that are used at various management levels. In our study, we cover the most important types of contemporary organizations: transaction processing systems, process control systems, enterprise resource planning, knowledge management systems, customer relationship management, management information systems, decision support systems, and executive information systems. Managers in organizations are interested in systems tailored to top management levels, as these assist them in planning and decision-making processes.

Keywords: *Information system types, Contemporary organization, Management Levels, Management information system, Decision support system*

Introduction

Global market globalization and internationalization have increased competitive pressures on businesses, leading them to engage in critical projects for their development and survival. These projects, such as implementing information technologies for information systems, all require careful management, planning, staffing, organization, monitoring, control, and evaluation. Information Systems (IS) are tailored to provide various benefits to enterprises and can be a crucial factor in their success, offering a competitive edge. However, some companies discover during implementation or operation that these systems are not helping them achieve their goals or are not performing as expected, prompting costly changes that can set the company back (Figueroa-Flores, 2020).

Received: 22 January 2024

Revised: 4 February 2024

Final Accepted 25 February 2024

Copyright © authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701386>

Contemporary organizations prioritize sustainability, agility, and exponential growth. They use information and communication technology to mitigate risks, cut costs, and boost profits. These organizations also understand the significance of embracing flexible and exponential thinking in their business models to fuel exponential growth (Rahman, 2022). Therefore, The use of technological systems has become essential for organizations aiming to enhance efficiency, productivity, and overall performance (Al-Tuhaifi, 2017).

Complex and fast-paced organizations, managing requires innovative approaches to cope with the expanding challenges in the economy, politics, and personal lives. Understanding the intricate relationships between various elements of a system is crucial. The "know-why" methodology offers a way to examine systems, their parts, and their interdependencies, aiding in understanding a specific organization's situation (Neumann, 2008).

In different management levels, Information systems supporting decision-making, improving efficiency, and enhancing communication within organizations. At the operational level, information systems help manage daily activities such as inventory control, transaction processing, and scheduling. They provide real-time data and automate routine tasks, improving operational efficiency and reducing errors (Laudon & Laudon, 2019).

At the tactical level, information systems support middle managers in making decisions that affect the organization's short-term goals. These systems provide reports and data analysis tools that help managers monitor performance, allocate resources, and make informed decisions to decisions to achieve strategic objectives (O'Brien, 2018).

At the strategic level, information systems support top-level executives in making long-term decisions that affect the overall direction of the organization. Strategic information systems provide decision support through tools such as data analytics, business intelligence, and strategic planning software. These systems help executives analyze market trends, forecast future performance, and develop competitive strategies (Turban et al., 2018).

Information system types

Transaction Processing Systems

Transaction processing systems (TPS) are critical for businesses because they manage the recurring transactions required for business operations at an organizational level. They support daily duties such as order processing, billing, payroll, and inventory management by efficiently and precisely processing a large volume of transactions to maintain smooth operations (Al-Mamary et al., 2014a). TPS are frequently employed in data processing systems and serve as the foundation for handling daily transactions. They record and execute regular transactions such as deposits, material flow, and sales, as well as update and regulate data in current computer systems. A breakdown in TPS, even if just temporarily, might cause failures throughout the corporation and its associated firms (Gray & Reuter, 1992).

Security is a crucial challenge for online transactions, which rely on programs such as SQL and other computer software to maintain confidentiality and comply to particular limits. Transactions using TPS can take place in batch processes, where data is gathered and saved for subsequent processing, or in online and immediate procedures, where databases are accessed in real time. TPS assists businesses in defining and structuring operational roles, resources, and objectives, allowing them to meet basic organizational expectations with up-to-date and correct

data. TPS duties include issuing credits to clients based on certain criteria, tracking transaction flows, handling employee payroll, and storing employee timesheets (Özkan et al., 2010).

Process Control Systems

Process control systems (PCS) are crucial for monitoring and managing industrial or physical processes such as petroleum refining, power generation, and steel manufacturing. For example, a petroleum refinery may utilize electronic sensors linked to computers to continuously monitor chemical processes and make real-time modifications to control the refinery process. These systems involve hardware, software, and operational processes (Laudon & Laudon, 2019).

PCS are another sort of data processing that is widely employed at both the operational and technical levels. PCS are used to monitor and control a variety of physical and industrial processes, including operating systems, computer applications, and equipment. While hardware control methods are common in most control systems, there is a clear shift toward more efficient software systems (Chuma, 2020). These software systems can vary in size from small, standalone apps to massive, network-connected systems. Utilizing essential database-based PCS capabilities can have a major impact on the system's scalability and responsiveness. These systems allow companies to handle and process massive amounts of data, obtain high data precision, and execute sophisticated calculations. PCSs are used in various industries, including power generating, chemical manufacture, and oil and gas processing. They use computer-linked sensors for continuous monitoring, allowing for rules and modifications to reach (Ciortea, 2004).

Enterprise Resource Planning System

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems help businesses manage resources effectively by integrating many business processes. These systems have various advantages, including improved decision-making accuracy, automated activities, and faster access to information. ERP systems are often made up of integrated software modules that work with a central database to facilitate data sharing between various departments and business activities such as finance, accounting, human resources, and sales. This centralized database is critical for ensuring that input data from one area of the company is immediately available to other processes (Laudon & Laudon, 2019).

Enterprise Collaboration Systems (ECS), often known as office automation systems, are another major type of enterprise system that is commonly utilized to aid managers with various duties. These systems facilitate collaboration and communication procedures among firm groups and employees, enabling activities such as electronic mail, video conferencing, and file transfer. While ERP systems have many advantages, they are not without restrictions. ERP systems may not cover all procedures in all industries, hence many organizations rely on custom solutions (Al-Mamary et al., 2014a).

ERP systems can also be restrictive because they frequently result in uniform processes for enterprises. Furthermore, ERP deployment can be time-consuming, spanning three to five years in large businesses. Other drawbacks include the usage of out-of-date technology, a lack of usability in terms of interface design, and limited benefits for interaction with some current object-oriented ERP systems. However, studies have shown that user training and assistance,

top management involvement, and team configurations can all have a major impact on ERP system performance and installation efficiency (Azevedo et al., 2012).

Knowledge Management System

Based on superior knowledge, a corporation can surpass its competition in its invention, manufacturing, and delivery processes. Companies should employ protected and controlled knowledge to accomplish these aims since effective knowledge management can boost a company's performance and innovation. Enterprises face the peril of knowledge loss and could not have sufficient procedures and frameworks to generate, preserve, employ, and disseminate their vital information for sustained prosperity. (Laudon & Laudon, 2019).

Information systems, specifically Knowledge Management Systems (KMSs), are key tools to address these challenges. KMSs enable companies to gather relevant and comprehensive knowledge and experience from internal or external sources, which can enhance decision-making and other critical processes (Gresty et al., 2013). These systems are closely related to collaboration systems, highlighting the importance of communication and knowledge sharing to make them effective and useful. Knowledge-based information includes qualitative and quantitative reports of past project experiences, providing lessons learned to help companies address issues during other challenges (Abdullah et al., 2008).

Customer Relationship Management system

When companies maintain constant contact with their customers through customer services, they can plan to enhance the services needed to improve customer satisfaction, leading to positive impacts on their efficiency and profitability. To achieve this, companies must address various requirements such as system, information, and service qualities. This is how Information Systems (IS) can improve customer services. Optimizing revenue, customer satisfaction, and retention in companies can be achieved through the implementation of Customer Relationship (Choi et al., 2013)

Management (CRM) systems. CRM systems help companies establish strong and long-lasting connections with their customers by organizing processes such as marketing, services, and sales administration based on customer-provided data. Information system-based CRM focuses on two main groups: current customers and potential new customers. For current customers, the goal is to provide better services, while for potential new customers, the focus is on identifying, attracting, and maintaining connections with them, ultimately leading to increased sales. Companies can improve the efficiency of their operations by implementing CRM systems, crossing both internal and external borders. CRM systems help collect and integrate data about customers, and the results of analyzing this data using CRM software serve as a communication method between the business and its customers (Laudon & Laudon, 2019).

Management Information Systems

Management Information Systems (MIS) are essential tools in all companies, aimed at quickly preparing information that is complete, reliable, understandable, and accessible. These systems automate tasks and improve the productivity, effectiveness, and efficiency of organizational processes. Automation through MIS can help companies save resources such as labor, money, and time. At the organizational level, MIS supports the control and monitoring of transaction

procedures from Transaction Processing Systems (TPS) at the office level. MIS utilizes data collected by TPS to generate control reports for administrators (Al-Tuhaifi and Kamoun-Chouk, 2024). MIS integrates various scientific aspects, including computer science, management science, and operations studies, to develop solutions for systems. In an MIS model, a database provided by information systems is used by software to generate periodic reports and mathematical models. These models simulate processes within the company, and the output of the simulation process helps managers address challenges. In organizational environments, MIS presents information to other members of the Inter-Organizational Information System (Al-Mamary et al. , 2014b).

The process of processes decision-making can utilize both main and sub-management information systems for various purposes. These systems can extract integrated information from a large database to assist decision-makers in improving operations or selecting new business opportunities to maximize profit. The role of Management Information Systems (MIS) in decision-making can be summarized as follows: First, MIS provides decision-makers with the necessary information. All managers can access this information using a formal computer system. MIS also integrates with other areas like decision support systems and knowledge-based systems to provide solutions. Second, by continuously supplying information to managers, MIS helps companies identify and understand system problems and analyze circumstances. MIS, as a day-to-day management system, offers several advantages, including providing appropriate answers to business issues, facilitating efficient association among company departments, and providing relevant data and documents. Additionally, MIS reduces the need for time and labor, improves organizational and departmental techniques, and replaces manual filing and analysis processes with quick and easy computer systems. These benefits result in more effective controlling, organizing, and planning systems, highlighting the vital role of MIS in businesses (Singh & Kaur, 2012).

Management information systems provide quick access to information for managers, including interaction with other decision support systems, information requests, external information cross-referencing, and possible data mining techniques. These systems can also compare strategic objectives to practical decisions, providing managers with insight into how well their decisions align with company strategy. The significant role of MIS in acquiring reliable data from enterprises. However, few organizations have actively embraced this role and served as models for others. Consequently, the improvement in decision-making based on the customization of useful information has been limited (Cock et al., 2020).

Decision Support Systems

Decision Support Systems (DSS) are computer-based systems designed to solve unique and rapidly changing problems by providing solutions that cannot be identified by the system alone. Interactive DSS software systems utilize information from various sources such as documents, raw data, business models, and individual knowledge to assist managers in decision-making processes and help them identify and address their problems. While Management Information Systems (MIS) can identify system issues and help decision-makers choose and evaluate suitable solutions, they may not meet the specific needs of decision-makers. DSS, on the other hand, caters to these particular requirements for individuals and groups of managers, adding value to the decision-making process and empowering managers to make special decisions such as explaining plans, introducing new products, and marketing (Jain & Raju., 2016).

DSS utilizes both internally obtained information from Transaction Processing Systems (TPS) and MIS, as well as external sources such as current stock prices and competitor's products. With this comprehensive information, DSS can estimate both technical and financial details for companies. For example, a DSS-based system for voyage estimation in a transportation company can calculate costs for ship/time for employees and port distances for financial and technical calculations. DSS can address specific questions such as the relationship between vessel speed, delivery schedules, and overall earnings to optimize the proposed system based on specific criteria (Asemi, et al., 2011).

Decision Support Systems (DSS) offer several benefits to companies in the decision-making process by alleviating various limitations and addressing related issues. DSS helps companies achieve more productive solutions, enhanced satisfaction, greater agility, innovation, and reliability in decision-making processes. Erozan (2019) highlighted the practical effects of fuzzy DSS on the reliability of components compared to common reliability functions. Improved maintenance works, especially for critical components, can enhance system reliability and credibility. Guo et al. (2020) used data mining technology in a specific decision support system and found that it can analyze various aspects of statistical data, leading to better and more satisfactory decisions.

Executive Information Systems

In organizations, the managers are tasked with making timely and appropriate decisions to address the company's challenges, especially in the increasingly competitive business environment. Executive Information Systems (EISs) are tools designed to provide the necessary information for this purpose. EISs are characterized by their flexibility, allowing them to adapt to changing issues and information needs. One of the main goals of EISs is to assist senior administrators in focusing on the most crucial information that directly impacts the company's success, efficiency, and profitability. These systems help senior managers make unplanned and infrequent decisions that require insight, judgment, and assessment. EISs provide quick access to a variety of internal and external information, including data from Transaction Processing Systems (TPS), Management Information Systems (MIS), Decision Support Systems (DSS), financial reports, and commercial sources, presenting the information in easy-to-use and understandable formats such as data and graphs (Salmeron et al., 2001).

The difference between Decision Support Systems (DSS) and EIS lies in their support functions. While DSS indirectly supports upper management by preparing the analysis requested by executives, EIS directly supports senior managers by providing vital information. DSS is limited in scope and focuses on specific decisions, which can result in a failure to provide a comprehensive view of the company compared to EIS decision-making. Developing an EIS involves two main aspects: first, a methodology for diagnosing the "real vital information" for a firm, and then the development of the system itself (Shim, 2000).

The use of Executive Information Systems (EIS) provides several advantages for companies. These systems are user-friendly, requiring minimal computer experience from administrators. EIS delivers timely summary information to the company, presenting data in an easy-to-understand and filtered format for managers. It enhances information tracking and improves decision-making efficiency. However, EIS also has disadvantages. It is dependent on the system and may lack functionality by design. Implementation costs for EIS are high, and the system can overload some managers with information. Managing these information systems

can be challenging due to their complexity, size, and speed limitations. EIS also requires appropriate internal procedures for data management, and the data provided may sometimes be insecure and less reliable (Leidner & Elam, 1993).

Information systems at various management levels

Figure (1)

In summary, information systems type are important in all management levels. As shown in Figure (1). Transaction Processing Systems (TPS) handling daily transactions like order processing and payroll, ensuring operational efficiency. Process Control Systems (PCS) monitor and control physical processes, crucial in industries like manufacturing. Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Systems integrate business processes, aiding decision-making and data sharing. Knowledge Management Systems (KMS) gather and organize knowledge for decision-making and innovation. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Systems manage customer interactions, enhancing services and satisfaction. Management Information Systems (MIS) provide timely information for decision-making and process improvement. Decision Support Systems (DSS) assist in complex decision-making with relevant information and tools. Executive Information Systems (EIS) offer critical data for strategic decisions to senior executives, presented in a user-friendly format. Each system contributes to efficiency, decision-making, and overall organizational success.

Conclusion

The integration of Information Systems (IS) in contemporary organizations has become increasingly crucial owing to the globalization and internationalization of markets, which have heightened competitive pressures. IS plays a significant role in managing critical projects, enhancing organizational effectiveness, and ensuring sustainability and growth. These systems provide various benefits to enterprises and offer them a competitive edge. On the other hand, various types of information systems in organizations are considered the primary tools for accomplishing tasks, planning, and predicting the future in contemporary organizations. These systems are distributed across different management levels because of the different functions and tasks of each system. Advanced and professional systems are designed to accommodate the analysis of big data and are tailored to higher management levels. There are types of information systems that are used at more than one management level because of their flexibility in meeting user needs and requirements, such as Management Information Systems (MIS) and Decision Support Systems (DSS). In general, there is agreement on the importance of information systems in all types at various management levels in contemporary organizations, where they are indispensable under all circumstances.

Reference

- Abdullah R, Ibrahim H, Atan R, Napis S, Selamat MH, Hairudin N. (2008). The development of bioinformatics knowledge management system with collaborative environment. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*. 8(2): 309-319.
- Al-Mamary YH, Shamsuddin A, Aziati N. (2014a). The role of different types of information systems in business organizations: A review. *International Journal of Research*. 1(7): 333-339 .
- Al-Mamary YH, Shamsuddin A, Aziati N. (2014b). The meaning of management information systems and its role in telecommunication companies in Yemen. *American Journal of Software Engineering*. 2(2): 22-25.
- Al-Tuhaifi, M. S. S. (2017). Factors influencing acceptance of technology in context of Yemen. *American Journal of Computer Science and Information Engineering*, 4 (1), 1–6.
- Al-Tuhaifi, M. S., Kamoun-Chouk, S. (2024). Main Factors Affecting Successful Adoption of Management Information System in Yemen Mobile Phone Enterprises. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 4 (1), 825–835.
- Anna P, (2015). "Contemporary organization and a perspective on integration and development," Working Papers 86/2015, Institute of Economic Research, revised Apr 2015.
- Asemi A, Safari A, Zavareh AA. (2011).The role of Management Information System (MIS) and Decision Support System (DSS) for manager's decision making process. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 6(7): 164-173.
- Azevedo PS, Romão M, Rebelo E. (2012). Advantages, limitations and solutions in the use of ERP systems (enterprise resource planning)-A case study in the hospitality industry. *Procedia Technology*. 5: 264-272.
- Choi W, Rho MJ, Park J, Kim K-J, Kwon YD, Choi IY. (2013). Information system success model for customer relationship management system in health promotion centers. *Healthcare Informatics Research*. 19(2): 110- 120.
- Chuma LL. (2020). The Role of Information Systems in Business Firms Competitiveness. *Integrated Review Paper from Business Perspective* .
- Ciordea M. (2004). Aspects regarding the types of process control systems. *International Conference on Theory and Applications of Mathematics and Informatics* .
- Erozan İ. (2019) A fuzzy decision support system for managing maintenance activities of critical components in manufacturing systems. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*. 52: 110-120.
- Figueroa-Flores, J. R., Gonzaga, E. A., & Ruiz-Ledesma, E. F. (2020). Causes of failure in the implementation and functioning of information systems in organizations. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(6)
- Gray J, Reuter A. (1992). *Transaction Processing: Concepts and Techniques*. Elsevier .
- Gresty M. (2013). What role do information systems play in the knowledge management activities of SMEs? *Business Information Review*. 30(3): 144-151.

- Guo Y, Wang N, Xu Z-Y, Wu K. (2020). The internet of things-based decision support system for information processing in intelligent manufacturing using data mining technology. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*. 142: 106630.
- Jain R, Raju S. (2016). *Decision Support System in Agriculture Using Quantitative Analysis*. Udaipur: Agrotech Publishing Academy.
- Kock A, Schulz B, Kopmann J, Gemünden HG (2020). Project portfolio management information systems' positive influence on performance—the importance of process maturity. *International Journal of Project Management*. 38(4): 229-241.
- Laudon KC, Laudon JP. (2019). *Management Information Systems. Managing the digital firm*: Pearson Educación.
- Leidner DE, Elam JJ. (1993). Executive information systems: their impact on executive decision making. *Journal of Management Information Systems*. 10(3): 139-155.
- Neumann K.(2008). *Know-why. Model Dein Glück*, Norderstedt: Books on Demand GmbH
- O'Brien, J. A., & Marakas, G. M. (2018). *Management Information Systems* (14th ed.).
- Özkan S, Bindusara G, Hackney R. (2010). Facilitating the adoption of e-payment systems: theoretical constructs and empirical analysis. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*.
- Rahman, H. (2022). Organizational Sustainability. In *Advances in Business Information Systems and Analytics* (pp. 72–102). IGI Global.
- Salmeron JL, Luna P, Martinez FJ. (2020). Executive information systems in major companies: Spanish case study. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*. 23(3): 195-207 .
- Shim JK. (2000). *Information Systems and Technology for the Noninformation Systems Executive: an Integrated Resource Management Guide for the 21st Century*. CRC Press .
- Singh K, Kaur B. (2012). Role of Management Information System in Business: Opportunities and Challenges. *Gian Jyot E-Journal*. 1(2).
- Turban, E., Pollard, C., Wood, G., & Chatterjee, S. (2018). *Information Technology for Management: On-Demand Strategies for Performance, Growth, and Sustainability* (11th ed.).